

Influence of Educational Chess on Executive Functions Such as Cognitive Flexibility, Inhibition and Working Memory

Influencia del Ajedrez Educativo en Funciones Ejecutivas como Flexibilidad Cognitiva, Inhibición y Memoria de Trabajo

Influência do Xadrez Educacional em Funções Executivas, como Flexibilidade Cognitiva, Inibição e Memória de Trabalho

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Abstract

Objective. Evaluate the influence that chess practice can have in an educational environment, on executive functions such as: cognitive flexibility, inhibition and working memory. **Method.** Sample composed of 301 boys and girls, aged between 10 and 14 years ($M=11.7$, $SD=1.3$), with 49% girls, 51% boys; Similarly, there was an experimental group ($N=157$) and a control group ($N=144$). For the evaluation, the BRIEF-2 questionnaire for behavioral evaluation of executive function was used. This instrument measures the different executive functions and the indices of behavioral regulation, emotional regulation, cognitive regulation and the global index of executive function. The pedagogical tool AJEDUCA (chess and education) was used, whose main objective is to facilitate the teaching of chess in the educational system. **Results.** The results showed a better performance of the boys and girls who practice chess, in the executive functions of inhibition, cognitive flexibility and working memory, with a statistically significant effect on the inhibition and flexibility scales; with the improvement of the results in favor of the experimental group in the family and in the school. **Conclusion.** Chess practice could improve the executive functions analyzed.

Keywords: Educational chess; executive functions; inhibition; cognitive flexibility; working memory.

Resumen

Objetivo. Evaluar la influencia que puede tener la práctica de ajedrez en un entorno educativo, sobre funciones ejecutivas como: la flexibilidad cognitiva, inhibición y memoria de trabajo. **Metodología.** Muestra compuesta por 301 niños y niñas, con edades comprendidas entre los 10 y 14 años ($M=11.7$, $DT=1.3$), con un 49% de niñas, 51% niños; de igual modo, se contó con un grupo experimental ($N=157$) y un grupo control ($N=144$). Para la evaluación se utilizó el cuestionario BRIEF-2 de evaluación conductual de la función ejecutiva. Este instrumento mide las distintas funciones ejecutivas y los índices de regulación conductual, regulación emocional, regulación cognitiva e índice global de función ejecutiva. Se utilizó la herramienta pedagógica AJEDUCA (ajedrez y educación) que tiene como objetivo principal facilitar la enseñanza del ajedrez en el sistema educativo. **Resultados.** Los resultados mostraron un mejor desempeño de los niños y niñas que practican el ajedrez, en las funciones ejecutivas de inhibición, flexibilidad cognitiva y memoria de trabajo; con un efecto estadísticamente significativo en las escalas de inhibición y flexibilidad, con la mejora de los resultados en favor del grupo experimental en familia y en escuela. **Conclusión.** La práctica de ajedrez podría mejorar las funciones ejecutivas analizadas.

Palabras clave: Ajedrez educativo; flexibilidad cognitiva; funciones ejecutivas; inhibición; memoria de trabajo.

Resumo:

Objetivo. Avaliar a influência que a prática do xadrez pode ter em ambiente educacional, nas funções executivas como: flexibilidade cognitiva, inibição e memória de trabalho. **Metodologia.** Amostra composta por 301 meninos e meninas, com idades entre 10 e 14 anos ($M=11,7$, $DP=1,3$), sendo 49% meninas, 51% meninos; Da mesma forma, houve um grupo experimental ($N=157$) e um grupo controle ($N=144$). Para a avaliação, foi utilizado o questionário BRIEF-2 para avaliação comportamental da função executiva. Este instrumento mede as diferentes funções executivas e os índices de regulação comportamental, regulação emocional, regulação cognitiva e o índice global de função executiva. Foi utilizada a ferramenta pedagógica AJEDUCA (xadrez e educação), cujo objetivo principal é facilitar o ensino do xadrez no sistema educacional.

Resultados. Os resultados mostraram um melhor desempenho dos meninos e meninas que praticam xadrez, nas funções executivas de inibição, flexibilidade cognitiva e memória de trabalho. Com efeito estatisticamente significativo nas escalas de inibição e flexibilidade, com melhora dos resultados a favor do grupo experimental na família e na escola. **Conclusão.** A prática do xadrez pode melhorar as funções executivas analisadas.

Palavras-chave: Xadrez educacional; flexibilidade cognitiva; Funções executivas; inibição; memória de trabalho.

Introduction

Because classical education programs do not provide sufficient opportunities for individual development, attempts to update existing programs have increased, through the introduction of new educational techniques, with the ultimate goal of better acquisition of knowledge at school age and preschool. One of these new techniques is the use of chess at an educational level, which has proven to be an excellent educational tool with beneficial factors ([Grau-Pérez & Moreira, 2017](#); [Picotita-Quezada et al., 2021](#)). According to the existing literature, the important benefits it provides can be divided into cognitive elements: concentration, memory and logical thinking, all essential skills for the development of each individual; critical thinking factors, such as improving the ability to assess strengths and weaknesses, make value judgments, and make decisions; and enhance creativity through problem solving ([García et al., 2022](#); [Torres, 2023](#)).

Understanding this importance, the European Parliament issued a declaration in 2012, requesting member states to support the introduction of the *Chess at School* program in their educational systems ([European Parliament, 2012](#)). In February 2015, the Spanish Congress of Deputies, through the Education and Sports Commission, unanimously approved a proposal that urges the Spanish Government, in collaboration with the Autonomous Communities, and in the exercise of that are their own, *to promote that Educational Administrations and educational centers include the practice of chess in their educational offer, with the advice of the Pedagogical Coordination Team, made up of experts in*

educational chess and linked to various entities and groups such as AJEDUCA, *Chess and Education* (Junta de Andalucía, 2017).

Theoretical framework

The concept of executive functions is understood as a multifaceted psychological construct, which can be represented as a set of related but separable high-level cognitive skills, possibly supported by the prefrontal cortex and implemented by larger brain networks (Miyake et al., 2000). However, although the number and type of executive functions that exist are a matter of debate, most authors agree that executive functions show high intra- and inter-individual variability in their cognitive and behavioral manifestations.

Executive functions take on special importance in the practice of chess, since these mental abilities allow human beings to organize, plan, monitor, check their cognitive and behavioral activity, enhancing neural processes and mental capacities in different areas of knowledge (Picotita-Quezada et al., 2021; Sandoval-Tipan & Ramos-Galarza, 2020).

In recent years, several studies have examined the influence of chess on executive functions such as planning and cognitive flexibility, understood as the brain's ability to easily adapt behavior and thinking to changing, novel and unexpected situations, or to the ability to think about several concepts at once (Holding & Reynolds, 1982; Saariluoma & Hohlfeld, 1994). Rojas Vidaurreta (2011) studied the relationship between chess and cognitive flexibility applying the Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST), in children players and non-players of chess, from 7 to 11 years old. The results showed that the chess-playing children completed more categories in this task, which meant a better performance in activities that require adjustment and change of focus of attention; which suggests a positive influence of chess on cognitive flexibility. This, in the game of chess, implies that the subject has to plan, reorganize and structure the moves, taking into account the established rules of the game and the unforeseen changes that may occur as a result of the opponent's action (Ramos et al., 2018). In the same direction, some studies have shown the benefits of playing chess and its influence on executive functions. These higher-order cognitive processes make it possible

to adapt to complex and novel contexts that go beyond routine responses, since they need control mechanisms to be dealt with effectively (Collette et al., 2006).

Grau-Pérez and Moreira (2017) investigated the impact of learning and practicing chess on two executive functions (planning and flexibility) in childhood, comparing the performance of a group of children who played chess with a group of children who did not practice chess. In a planning test (Tower of London) and in a cognitive flexibility test (WCST). The results established a better performance of the children chess players in planning and in the analysis of some differences in flexibility.

In this way, it is worth asking: could the teaching of chess improve academic performance? The proposed explanations refer to the fact that chess is a cognitively demanding activity. Chess requires domain-general cognitive skills that can be trained by playing the game. So those cognitive abilities could be transferred to other domains. For example, Bart (2014) suggests that chess engages, and possibly enhances, cognitive abilities such as working memory, fluid intelligence, and the ability to concentrate.

A recent meta-analysis has evaluated the efficacy of chess teaching (Sala & Gobet, 2016), including 24 studies and 40 effect sizes, showing that chess seems to improve the performance of primary and secondary students in mathematics ($\bar{d} = 0.38$) and general cognitive ability ($\bar{d} = 0.34$).

In relation to the inhibition executive category, it is known that it is an important factor in a chess game, to the extent that the subject must be able to pay attention, select the most convenient move and inhibit the inappropriate ones, not rushing to make a move without consider the possible consequences. In this sense, the inhibition capacity is vital learning during childhood, and the practice of chess requires inhibitory processes, which may imply a positive influence (Ramos et al., 2018). Gindi & Pilpel (2020) investigated whether chess experience is related to inhibitory control in adolescents with and without attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), finding that chess players were less impulsive than non-chess players, regardless of the diagnosis.

Joireman et al. (2002) examined the relationship between scores on the Sensation Seeking Scale (*Sensation Seeking Scale*, SSS) (Zuckerman, 2015) and chess participation in university students. Observing how, students who had played chess, and those with more chess experience, showed higher scores, regardless of gender. Higher disinhibition scores were also associated with greater chess experience. In general, people who score higher on the SSS scale tend to be people who show an aversion to routine activities and are more involved in new and riskier activities.

It is also known that the working memory category is involved in the game of chess, insofar as the subjects show superior performance (Ramos et al., 2018). Along the same lines, Robbins et al. (1996) found a higher performance in children who practiced chess, specifically in memory tasks. Working memory is implicit in the selection of movements and sequences of movements to decide the suitability of one over another (Ramos et al., 2018).

If it is taken into account that executive functions are an essential part of the ability to think about a specific goal or objective, and to organize the means to achieve it, a relationship can be established between the main executive components and the different actions that are carried out in practice in the game of chess (Beldarrain & Ustároz, 2012), as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between the main executive components and the mental activities that are put into practice in the game of chess..

General mental activities (for life)	Mental activities associated with chess	Executive functions involved
Predict the future, carry out tests and simulations within our brain and anticipate the consequences of the acts that are going to be carried out	- Mental representation of movements	- Planning - Work memory

	- What would happen if I made this move?	- Work memory
Imagine alternative actions and assess chances of success	- What moves could my opponent make? - What could be my alternative answers?	- Cognitive flexibility - Inhibitory control
Concentrate on the key points, plan, order and sequence the actions that must be followed in a specific time	- learned openings	- Planning - Work memory
Solve problems as they arise and improvise	- Change before an unforeseen movement	- Cognitive flexibility
Assess whether our actions are feasible from an economic, social or moral point of view	- Valuation of the exchange/sacrifice of pieces	- Decision making
Rethink the situation and change your attitude, be flexible if the plan does not go as agreed	- Change of strategy in the game	- Cognitive flexibility

Note: Own elaboration based on Beldarrain and Ustárroz, 2012

The final objective of this study is to evaluate the possible influence of educational chess, as a pedagogical tool, on executive functions, inhibition, cognitive flexibility and working memory.

Method

Population and sample

The sample was made up of 301 children from the third cycle of Primary Education (5th and 6th) and from 1st and 2nd of Compulsory Secondary Education, aged between 10 and 14 years ($M=11.7$, $SD=1.3$) being 49% girls and 51 % boys. The study was carried out with an experimental group ($N=157$) and a control group ($N=144$), belonging to four public centers in the province of Seville (Spain), the two primary education centers were located in rural areas and the two of secondary education in urban areas.

Instrument

For the behavioral assessment of executive function, the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function instrument was used (BRIEF-2) (Gioia et al., 2017). This instrument measures the different executive functions and the indices of behavioral regulation, emotional regulation, cognitive regulation and the global index of executive function. It is a questionnaire with a list of behaviors that is applied to parents and teachers (informants) of children between 5 and 18 years of age, and that allows professionals to assess behaviors associated with alterations in these functions in the family and school environments (Maldonado Belmonte, 2016).

It has two versions, one to be answered by the mother, father or other relatives (BRIEF-2 Family) and another to be answered by the teachers of the person evaluated (BRIEF-2 School). Both versions have the same structure of validity scales, clinical scales and global indices. The clinical scales are combined into three general indices (Behavioral Regulation Index, Emotional Regulation Index, and Cognitive Regulation Index), which, in turn, are summarized in the Global Executive Function Index. Obtaining high scores on any of the BRIEF-2 scales indicates the presence of problems in the area represented by said scale (Gioia et al., 2017).

The pedagogical tool AJEDUCA (chess and education) was also used, whose main objective is to facilitate the teaching of chess in the educational system by providing teachers with a tested methodology, adapted to the different ages and levels of students, as well as cooperative activities, transversal and resources (Escobar & Escobar, 2018). All the material is ordered in a simple way to teach chess classes, with real objectives, not very extensive, so that the participating students can progress correctly in learning the game.

Procedure

The teachers of the centers in charge of applying the AJEDUCA tool (experimental group) were instructed to put it into practice, for one hour a week, during school hours, in a complete school year.

The families responsible for all the students who participated gave their signed consent prior to the procedure.

Prior to the AJEDUCA intervention and after its implementation, the described instrument (BRIEF-2) was administered to both the control and experimental groups. While the experimental group received didactic training from AJEDUCA, the control group carried out other types of activities, depending on the centers and their organization.

To determine the effect of chess on the scales, ANOVA tests of two factors were carried out with repeated measures in one of them, which will allow studying the effect that intra-subject factors (time: basal and final) and intersubject (group) and their interaction.

The level of significance was set at 5% (p value <0.05). Data analysis was performed using the SPSS Program version 25.

Results, analysis and discussion

[Table 2](#) shows the results for the dimensions of the BRIEF-2 Family scale. Statistically significant effects were observed in the clinical scales of inhibition (p=0.001 and p=0.001) and flexibility (p=0.003 and p=0.0001), but not in working memory (p=0.640 and p=0.842). The tests showed that the time effect was statistically significant, indicating that the values of the scales decreased significantly during the study, regardless of the group.

Table 2: Means, standard deviations (SD) and statistical contrasts, processes and variables of the BRIEF-2 Family according to group.

	Measurement , mean (SD)		Within- subject effects	
	PRE	POST	Weather	Group*Time
			<i>F</i> (gl.); <i>p</i> -value (η^2)	<i>F</i> (gl.); <i>p</i> -value (η^2)
Inhibition			<i>F</i> (1,170) = 10.56;	<i>F</i> (1,170) = 11.65;
			<i>p</i> = 0.001 (0.03)	<i>p</i> = 0.001 (0.033)
Control	50.01 (11.2)	49.85 (10.6)		
Experimental	50.53 (9.5)	44.86 (9.9)		
Total	50.27 (10.2)	47.36 (10.2)		
Flexibility			<i>F</i> (1,170) = 0.36;	<i>F</i> (1,170) = 1.46;
			<i>p</i> = 0.003 (0.028)	<i>p</i> = 0.001 (0.032)
Control	51.36 (10.1)	50.89 (10.2)		
Experimental	51.33 (10.7)	46.72 (11.4)		
Total	51.34 (10.4)	48.81 (10.9)		
Working memory			<i>F</i> (1,170) = 0.22;	<i>F</i> (1,170) = 0.04;
			<i>p</i> = 0.640 (0.001)	<i>p</i> = 0.842 (0.000)
Control	48.88 (10.7)	49.03 (10.8)		
Experimental	49.43 (10.7)	49.81 (9.7)		
Total	49.20 (10.7)	49.48 (10.1)		

Note: gl.: degrees of freedom. η^2 : partial squared eta (effect size).

However, there was a significant effect of the interaction of group and time, which indicates that the passage of time had a different influence, depending on whether they participated in the experimental group or not (Figure 1). Thus, in the experimental group, the inhibition and flexibility values decreased significantly at the end of the study with respect to the initial values, denoting the improvement achieved, while in the control group the values did not undergo significant changes. In both scales, the values reached at the end of the study by the students of the experimental group were statistically significantly lower than those of the control group.

[Insert Figure 1]

Table 3 shows the results for the dimensions of the BRIEF-2 School scale. Statistically significant effects were observed in the clinical scales of inhibition ($p=0.026$ and $p=0.015$), flexibility ($p=0.028$ and $p=0.017$) and working memory ($p=0.042$ and $p=0.014$). The tests showed that the time effect was statistically significant, indicating that the values of the scales decreased significantly during the study, regardless of the group.

Table 3: Means, standard deviations (SD) and statistical contrasts processes and variables of the BRIEF-2 School according to group.

	Measurement , mean (SD)		Within- subject effects	
	PRE	POST	Weather	Group*Time
			<i>F</i> (gl.); <i>p</i> -value (η^2)	<i>F</i> (gl.); <i>p</i> -value (η^2)
Inhibition			<i>F</i> (1,230) = 5.05;	<i>F</i> (1,230) = 6.03;
			<i>p</i> = 0.026 (0.011)	<i>p</i> = 0.015 (0.014)
Control	48.32 (10.1)	47.49 (11.9)		
Experimental	49.02 (11.8)	44.50 (15.0)		
Total	48.67 (11.1)	46.00 (13.7)		
Flexibility			<i>F</i> (1,227) = 4.89;	<i>F</i> (1,227) = 5.79;
			<i>p</i> = 0.028 (0.01)	<i>p</i> = 0.017 (0.012)
Control	51.24 (10.5)	50.84 (11.3)		
Experimental	51.41 (11.6)	46.46 (13.2)		
Total	51.33 (11.1)	47.65 (12.4)		
Working memory			<i>F</i> (1,230) = 4.20;	<i>F</i> (1,230) = 6.19;
			<i>p</i> = 0.042 (0.018)	<i>p</i> = 0.014 (0.026)
Control	51.23 (10.1)	50.31 (11.8)		
Experimental	50.80 (10.5)	47.06 (13.6)		
Total	51.02 (10.3)	48.69 (12.8)		

Note: gl .: degrees of freedom. η^2 : partial squared eta (effect size).

There was also a significant effect of the interaction of group and time, which indicates that the passage of time had a different influence, depending on whether they participated in the experimental group or not (Figure 2). In the experimental group, the values of the scales and the index decreased significantly at the end of the study with respect to the initial values, also denoting the improvement achieved, while in the control group the values did not undergo significant changes. In the scales and the index, the values reached at the end of the study by the students of the experimental group were statistically significantly lower than those of the control group.

[Insert Figure 2]

The results for the dimensions of the BRIEF-2 Family and BRIEF-2 School scales indicate that there are statistically significant effects on the inhibition and flexibility scales, taking into account that, due to the characteristics of the instrument used, the lower scores obtained by the experimental group suggest improvement in the executive components under study. In this research, it is observed that there is a difference of 4.99 points in inhibition and 4.17 points in flexibility in the scores of the BRIEF-2 Family scale with respect to the control group. However, almost no difference was found in the working memory component, with 0.78 points.

The inhibition and flexibility data coincide with the BRIEF-2 School scales, where an improvement (lower score) is also observed in the inhibition (2.99 points) and flexibility (4.38 points) components of the experimental group compared to the control group. In this case, statistically significant differences were observed in the BRIEF-2 Escuela scale, related to the executive working memory component, with an improvement of 3.25 points in the experimental group over the control group.

Since the Inhibition scale assesses the ability to stop, resist or stop an impulse and the ability to inhibit one's behavior at the right time. High scores are recorded on this scale in children who do not control their impulses well, with a tendency to interrupt or alter group activities, and general difficulty in *thinking before acting* (Maldonado Belmonte, 2016), which is equivalent in the intervention program AJEDUCA to "touched piece, moved piece" (Escobar & Escobar, 2018,

p. 57).

The results obtained are in agreement with those reported by [Ramos et al. \(2018\)](#), where differences were found between the experimental and control group of chess practitioners, the former being the ones that obtained a better result. The data suggest that the executive inhibition component, in the game of chess, would become relevant at the moment in which the subject must select the most suitable movement and inhibit the inappropriate ones, without rushing and considering the possible consequences, that is, being able to delay or stop an automated response based on demands; in other words, controlling irrelevant information at will ([Rubiales et al., 2010](#)). In the same way, [Rojas Vidaurreta \(2011\)](#) found that children who practice chess present better scores in tasks that assess inhibition compared to those who do not practice it.

The flexibility scale assesses the ability to freely change from one situation, activity, or aspect, from one problem to another if circumstances so require. It implies the ability to make changes, alternating attention, and change of focus from one mental state to another ([Maldonado Belmonte 2016](#)). In other words, the player would have the ability to imagine alternative actions and assess chances of success, giving answers to questions such as: what would happen if I made this move? What moves could my opponent make? What could my answers be? alternatives? ([Beldarrain & Ustárroz, 2012](#)).

The data suggest an improvement in the flexibility scale, which would also be in line with the results obtained by [Rojas Vidaurreta \(2011\)](#), [Grau-Pérez and Moreira \(2017\)](#), [Ramos et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Jiménez Serna \(2019\)](#), in which it was shown that the cognitive flexibility results of the subjects who received chess training were better compared to those who did not practice chess.

In the same direction, data from various investigations ([Dvoretzky et al., 2003](#); [Karpov & Matsukevich, 2016](#); [McDonald, 2004](#); [Nimzowitch, 2009](#)), suggest that subjects who practice chess have better cognitive flexibility, which indicates that chess demands this process during the game, both for the change of mental process, going from memory to calculation and vice versa, but also to propose, assess and update the established plans during all phases of the game.

The studies by [Unterrainer et al. \(2006\)](#) found no significant differences between chess players and non-practitioners in working memory; In this sense, it should be noted that, in our study, in the BRIEF-2 Family scale, no significant differences were observed between the control and experimental groups, although they were found in the BRIEF-2 School scale, of the experimental group (47 .06 points) compared to the control group (50.31 points). This improvement would be in line with the data obtained in the research carried out by [Sandoval-Tipan & Ramos-Galarza \(2020\)](#), where there was a notable difference in terms of the natural and normalized score in a sample of 60 students, of which half practiced chess and the other half did not.

The group of chess players presented a better working memory performance. This could be explained by taking into account that the children, through chess training, would gradually develop an adequate memorization of the different moves learned, thanks to the different activities linked to AJEDUCA (openings, different strategies that are acquired as a result of the constant practice, different possibilities of making the movements of the pieces according to the position of the player himself and his opponent, etc.). The positioning of the player from the strategic point of view is done at the expense of the combination of factors that are stored from the memory processes, and its recall will depend on the deployment of this set of executive functions, in which the visual memory It's fundamental. Along the same lines, [Robbins et al. \(1996\)](#) support the preponderant role of the visuospatial component (ability to say where objects are in space) and central executive of working memory in the practice of chess, coinciding with the research carried out by [Aciego et al. \(2012\)](#), where memory and visuospatial skills were better in chess practitioners compared to children and adolescents who practice soccer or basketball.

Limitations and recommendations

It would be interesting to check the impact of the AJEDUCA pedagogical tool, after a longer implementation time (length of learning and training). Significant improvements are likely to be detected, since the effectiveness of chess in improving intellectual abilities in girls and boys seems to depend on the duration of training. It would be convenient to work directly on these variables in

future research. Therefore, it is established as a future objective, to extend the training period with the AJEDUCA pedagogical tool, as well as the number of participating subjects, varying the contexts in which it is applied, in order to know the moment in which they begin to appear improvements in the executive components analyzed. Examining various measures of chess skills (eg, piece positioning, tactics, strategy) is required to link specific chess activities to particular cognitive/academic skills. A systematic measurement scheme is required that relates the amount of chess instruction (for example: 15, 30, 45h, etc.) and the duration of the effect (0, 6, 12 months, etc.). Such a design would make a great contribution to the understanding of the Chess Effect.

The validation of chess as an educational tool should be the subject of further investigation. Rigorous experimental designs are needed to shed more light on possible placebo effects of chess teaching, the cognitive mechanisms underlying the transfer of chess skills to other domains, and the appropriate type and duration of teaching for it to occur. this transfer.

Conclusions

Based on the instruments used and the procedure performed, it was possible to measure the executive functions, inhibition, cognitive flexibility and working memory of students between the ages of 10 and 14, both practitioners and non-practitioners of chess. The clinical scales of inhibition and flexibility coincide in the improvement of the results in favor of the experimental group, from the observation of the two informants (Family and School).

Regarding the working memory category, improvement was only observed in BRIEF-2 School, with a statistically significant improvement in favor of the experimental group.

The results obtained suggest that the practice of educational chess could influence, and even improve, the executive functions under study. The practice of chess could help the development of cognitive skills for solving problems from other domains, in decision-making processes in complex and varied contexts (cognitive flexibility, inhibition and working memory).

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